

Role of Cryostat in Diagnostic Histopathology-Ten Years Experience at GMKMCH, SalemVajravelu Jayanthi¹, R. Kalpana², C. Aja³, J. Sujatha⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Mohan Kumaramangalam Medical College and Hospital, Salem, Tamilnadu²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Mohan Kumaramangalam Medical College and Hospital, Salem, Tamilnadu³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Stanley Medical College, Chennai, Tamilnadu⁴Professor and Head of the Department of Pathology, Government Mohan Kumaramangalam Medical College and Hospital, Salem, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Frozen sectioning using cryostat plays a vital role in the rapid diagnosis of intraoperative surgical procedures. Since the diagnosis is made within less than 20-30 minutes it helps the surgeon to make intra operative decision when the patient is on table for surgery.**Aim:** The present study aims to assess the role of cryostat in diagnostic histopathology and by comparing the frozen section (FS) diagnosis with that of formalin fixed routinely processed paraffin tissue section (PTS) diagnosis and to analyse the causes of discordance and thereby to minimise the errors.**Materials and Methods:** This retrospective study for 10 years duration includes 263 cases received for of FS diagnosis in dept of pathology at GMKMC, Salem, Tamilnadu. FS were taken using cryostat at -17°C and stained with haematoxylin and eosin. The FS diagnosis was compared with their corresponding PTS diagnosis and analysed for concordance and discordance.**Results:** Out of total 263 cases of frozen sections studied, 250 were concordant and 13 were discordant with their corresponding paraffin tissue sections. The discordant cases could be due to interpretation error, sampling error and communication error.**Conclusion:** By improving the technique of grossing the specimen sent for frozen section, maintaining adequate needed temperature of -17 °C inside the cryostat, quality of frozen tissue sections, staining quality, pathologist having good rapport with the operating surgeon all will improve the concordance rate and by minimising the various errors need of resurgery will be reduced and patient can be treated more efficiently.**Keywords:** Frozen Section, Cryostat, Concordant, Discordant.

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Introduction

Frozen section plays a vital role in the rapid diagnosis of Intraoperative/ on table surgical procedures. The very first frozen section was accomplished by a pathologist Mr. William H. Wetch in 1891 at John Hopkins Hospital. Over the last almost 130 years frozen section has evolved from a novelty to an accepted even mundane part of surgical pathology.[1]

The technique of taking frozen tissue sections were made comfortable by using a cryostat which has a freezing microtome kept inside a cabinet with a temperature maintained in the range of -15° C to -20° C.

The main use of frozen section is to diagnose rapidly within minutes, so that the surgeon can be guid-

ed during his surgery to make intra operative decision. The indications of frozen section are very many which include identification of tissue, nature of the lesion and to evaluate the surgical margins particularly in malignancies. Other indications include Enzyme Histochemistry, Immunoflorescence and Immunohistochemistry.[2]

Materials and Methods

This is a retrospective study for a period of ten years from January 2013 to December 2022 with a sample size of 263 cases whose frozen sections (FS) were analysed and compared with the diagnosis of corresponding routinely processed paraffin embedded permanent tissue sections reported in Dept of Pathology, Govt Mohan Kumaramangalam

Medical College hospital, Salem, TN. The datas were recovered from the registers maintained in Dept of Pathology. The tissues received from various surgical and superspeciality departments from our hospital to the Dept of Pathology, with written request having necessary laboratory/radiological/clinical details would be obtained one day prior to surgery and cryostat machine (Leica CM1510S) would be kept ready with -17 °C maintained at the time of receiving the surgical resected specimens. Tissue sections were cut at 3-4micron thickness followed by Haematoxilin and Eosin staining. Intraoperative histopathological diagnosis was made and informed to the operating surgeon with the average turnaround time being 20 minutes. Subsequently the specimens were fixed in

10% Buffered neutral formalin and routinely processed and paraffin embedded permanent tissue sections were cut at 0.4micron thickness using Leica microtome (Leica RM2255) and statined with Haematoxilin and Eosin and final histopathological diagnosis was made and correlated with their corresponding frozen section diagnosis.

Results

Over a period of 10 years from 2013 to 2022, a total of 263 cases were analysed of which 250 cases of (95.06%) frozen section diagnosis was concordant with their paraffin embedded permanent tissue sections and 13 (4.94%) cases were discordant. Out of 263 cases, 88 were from breast lesions of which 5 cases were discordant.

Table 1: Year Wise Frozen Section Cases Received

Year	Male	Female	Total	Concordant	Discordant
2013	1	13	14	13	1
2014	3	13	16	15	1
2015	3	12	15	13	2
2016	4	25	29	28	1
2017	8	35	43	43	nil
2018	6	38	44	41	3
2019	10	31	41	40	1
2020	nil	11	11	10	1
2021	10	18	28	26	2
2022	6	16	22	21	1
10 yrs	51	212	263	250	13

Out of the 5 discordant breast cases ,1 case of Ductal Carcinoma In Situ (DCIS) reported in Frozen Section was later diagnosed as Infiltrating Ductal Carcinoma in paraffin embedded tissue sections.3 cases of resected margin in Modified Radical Mastectomy specimen reported free of tumor in Frozen

Section were later diagnosed as infiltrative margins in paraffin embedded tissue sections.1 case of lumpectomy specimen which was reported in Frozen Section as negative for malignancy was latter diagnosed as papillary Ductal Carcinoma In Situ in paraffin embedded tissue sections.

Table 2: Frozen Sections Studied, Site wise

Organ	No of FS Cases Studied	Concordant	Discordant
Breast	88	83	5
Lymph node	30	29	1
Ovary	52	49	3
Thyroid	25	23	2
Salivary gland	2	1	1
Soft tissue	10	10	Nil
Skin margins for wide local excision	21	21	Nil
Kidney	5	5	Nil
Vulva	1	Nil	1
Testis	3	3	Nil
GIT	2	2	Nil
Endometrium	1	1	Nil
Liver	1	1	Nil
Pancreas	9	9	Nil
Gall bladder	1	1	Nil
CNS	12	12	Nil
Total	263	250	13

Out of 30 cases from lymphnode 29 were concordantly, reported as negative for metastatic deposits both in FS and in paraffin sections .1 case which was reported as NHL in FS was later diagnosed as HL, mixed cellularity variant in paraffin sections.

Ovary specimens received for 52 cases of which 3 cases were discordant those being 1 case of Granulosa cell tumour reported in FS was later diagnosed as High-Grade Serous Carcinoma in paraffin sections.1 case of Borderline Mucinous Tumour in FS were later reported as Mucinous carcinoma in paraffin sections.1 case of Borderline Serous Tumour

in FS was reported as Borderline Serous Tumour with focal invasion. Out of 25 cases from thyroid 2 were discordant. One being papillary carcinoma Thyroid which was missed in FS and reported as Nodular Colloid Goitre and 1 case of Follicular Adenoma was reported as Nodular Colloid Goitre in FS. 1 case of Pleomorphic Adenoma in Frozen Section from Parotid gland mass was reported as Fibrolipoma in paraffin sections.

1 case from vulval mass was reported as fibrocollagenous tissue in Frozen Section was later reported as Angiomyxoma in paraffin sections.

Table 3: List of Discordant Cases and Various Types of Errors

Organ	No	Frozen Section Diagnosis	Paraffin Embedded Tissue Sections Diagnosis	Type Of Error
Breast-MRM Resected margins	3	Free from tumour	Infiltrating margins	Sampling error
Breast mass	1	DCIS	IDC	Sampling error
Breast mass	1	Negative for malignancy	Papillary DCIS	Sampling error
Thyroid	1	Nodular colloid goitre	Papillary carcinoma thyroid	Sampling error/communication error
Thyroid	1	Nodular colloid goitre	Follicular adenoma	Sampling error/communication error
Lymph Node	1	Non-Hodgkins Lymphoma	Hodgkins Lymphoma (mixed cellularity)	Interpretation error
Vulva	1	Fibrocollagenous tissue	Angiomyxoma	sampling error
parotid	1	Pleomorphic adenoma	Fibrolipoma	Interpretation error
Ovary	1	Granulosa Cell tumour	High Grade Serous Carcinoma	Interpretation error
Ovary	1	Borderline Mucinous tumour	Mucinous carcinoma	Sampling error
Ovary	1	Borderline Serous tumour	Borderline Serous tumour with focal invasion	Interpretation error/sampling error
Total	13			

Discussion

The frozen sectioning using cryostat involves various steps including surgical resection, how quick the specimen is sent from Operation Theatre to pathology lab, sectioning at appropriate thickness, staining and microscopic evaluation, Communication with the operating surgeon and finally the most important being the experience of pathologist. Pitfalls may occur in any of the above steps. The errors could be due to the freezing artefact, site of sampling and interpretation by the pathologist. However, the overall diagnostic accuracy of frozen section using the cryostat has served as an integral part of quality assurance.[3] The commonest indication of frozen section in our study is to diagnose the presence of malignancy in Breast, Ovary and in Lymphnodes and resection margins status for the presence of malignancy. Margin clearance of malignant lesion is very crucial in terms of recurrence of tumours and their further management.[3]

The quality of frozen section taken from cryostat holds very essential part in the diagnosis. Our study has the accuracy rate of 95.05% which falls within

the range of 92%-97.98% from various studies in literature [4]. The average turnaround time in our study was 20 minutes whereas other studies have reported a range of 20-25 minutes [5].

The reason for 5 discordant lesions out of 88 breast cases could be due to sampling error where IDC from the main lesion and resected margins were missed in frozen sections. Papillary DCIS missed in frozen section was also due to sampling error. 3 discordant cases out of 52 cases from ovaries could also be attributed to inadequate sampling from solid areas during frozen section study. The infiltration into the ovarian stroma was missed in mucinous tumour. Adequate sampling of solid areas in ovarian tumours is necessary to rule out invasion particularly in mucinous tumours [6,7,8,9]

The High-grade serous carcinoma reported in paraffin sections was reported as Granulosa cell tumour in frozen section is due to interpretation error which could be due to freezing artefacts or sectioning defects or inexperience on the part of pathologist which are definitely preventable errors.[5]

Figure.1 Frozen Section -Hematoxylin and Eosin stain
a)Borderline Mucinous Tumor b)Schwannoma c)Granulosa Cell Tumor d)Nodular Goiter with Thyroiditis

Figure 1:

As far as the thyroid is concerned, 2 discordant cases out of 25 cases were both reported as nodular colloid goitre in frozen section latter reported in paraffin sections as papillary carcinoma encapsulated variant in one case and follicular Adenoma in the other case in paraffin sections. In both these cases suspicion of neoplasm or carcinoma from surgeon was not received in the cryo request form.

This is due to communication error between the surgeon and pathologist which is 100% preventable error.[6,7,8,9] Ground glass appearance of the nuclei as an artefact produced during formalin fixation is a diagnostic feature which is absent in frozen sections[2,3]. Also frozen sections distort the architecture of blood vessels leading to identify angiogenesis very difficult which is best assessed in permanent paraffin embedded sections.[2]

1 out of 30 cases from lymphnode was reported as NHL in frozen section was later reported in paraffin section as HL, Mixed cellularity variant. This could be due to interpretation error. 1 out of 2 cases from salivary gland was reported as Pleomorphic adenoma turned out as fibrolipoma in paraffin section. This could be due to interpretation error. 1 case from vulval mass, small biopsy was sent from

Gynaecology dept was reported as fibrocollagenous tissue in FS. The entire Excision biopsy specimen was latter reported as angiomyxoma in formalin fixed routinely processed paraffin sections. This could be due to sampling error from the operating surgeon.

Continuous monitoring and periodical quality assurance should be maintained in all pathology depts to identify the various errors and thereby minimizing them.[8]

Conclusion

Frozen sectioning using cryostat is a rapid, reliable and highly accurate method for intraoperative diagnosis.

Careful macroscopic inspection, adequate and representative sampling by pathologist, taking precautions in temperature maintained inside the cryostat, sectioning with proper staining, good interpersonal communication between the operating surgeon and reporting pathologist, correlation with serological and radiological findings and improving the knowledge of pathologist will altogether help us to reduce various errors of frozen section and cryostat serves as an indispensable tool in taking the frozen

sections in every tertiary care hospital helping the surgeon to decide or modify the surgical treatment intraoperatively thereby reducing the incidence of avoidable recurrent surgeries.

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